

2nd policy questionnaire: KEY DOCUMENTS

Task 4.1 on the political economy of land use change focuses on understanding the institutional setting in each of the case studies. From an institutional perspective, policies are formal rules that frame and constrain the decision-making environment.

Here we would like to ask you to indicate **which of the listed documents from the 1st questionnaire** you consider **most important** in the context of your **practice case**. The following questionnaire includes questions on aims and objectives, decision-making powers, implementation, responsibilities and stakeholders, etc.

Please fill in the questionnaires for **at least 2 documents**.

* Required

1. Indicate the PLUS Change practice case *

- Amsterdam (NL)
- Flanders (BE)
- Green Karst (SL)
- Île-de-France Region (FR)
- Kaigu peatland (LV)
- Lucca (IT)
- Mazovia Region (PL)
- Nitra City (SK)
- Parc Ela (CH)
- South Moravia (CZ)
- Surrey (UK)
- Three Countries Park (DE, BE, NL)

2. Title of the policy document *

3. What specific targets are stated in the document? Here, a target refers to specific measurable objectives (both quantitative and qualitative) *

4. What specific measures are set out in the document? Here, a measure refers to actions or means to achieve the specific objectives (both quantitative and qualitative). *

5. Are there mechanisms to monitor and/or evaluate the implementation of the policy document? If yes, please briefly describe them. *

6. Are there any indicators or benchmarks set for the monitoring and/or evaluation? If yes, please briefly describe them. *

7. What is the timeframe for the implementation of the policy document? (search for details of timelines in the document if available) *

- less than 5 years
- 5-10 years
- more than 10 years
- information not available

8. How would you characterise the public inclusion in the process of policy document development and approval? *

- Directive (public only informed or not communicated to public at all)
- Consultation (limited participation)
- Partnership (public as a stakeholder)
- Delegation of power (public as a decision maker)
- Other

9. Which stakeholders have the decision-making power? *

- central government authority
- regional government authority
- local government authority
- professional agencies (e.g., nature protection, spatial development, etc.)
- natural resources management (e.g., water or forest managers, technical infrastructure, etc.)
- private sector (e.g., developers, manufacturing, etc.)
- non governmental sector
- citizens (public)
- Other

10. Which stakeholders can influence the decision-making process, but do not have direct decision-making powers themselves? *

- central government authority
- regional government authority
- local government authority
- professional agencies (e.g., nature protection, spatial development, etc.)
- natural resources management (e.g., water or forest managers, technical infrastructure, etc.)
- private sector (e.g., developers, manufacturing, etc.)
- non governmental sector
- citizens (public)
- Other

11. Who is responsible for the implementation of the policy document? (search for responsible authorities or actors if available) *

- central government authority
- regional government authority
- local government authority
- professional agencies (e.g., nature protection, spatial development, etc.)
- natural resources management (e.g., water or forest managers, technical infrastructure, etc.)
- private sector (e.g., developers, manufacturing, etc.)
- non governmental sector
- citizens (public)
- Other

12. Which stakeholder groups are the most positively influenced by the implementation of this policy document? *

- central government authority
- regional government authority
- local government authority
- professional agencies (e.g., nature protection, spatial development, etc.)
- natural resources management (e.g., water or forest managers, technical infrastructure, etc.)
- private sector (e.g., developers, manufacturing, etc.)
- non governmental sector
- citizens (public)
- Other

13. Specify what are the positive influences of the policy implementation on the above indicated stakeholders *

14. Which stakeholder groups are the most negatively influenced by the implementation of this policy document? *

- central government authority
- regional government authority
- local government authority
- professional agencies (e.g., nature protection, spatial development, etc.)
- natural resources management (e.g., water or forest managers, technical infrastructure, etc.)
- private sector (e.g., developers, manufacturing, etc.)
- non governmental sector
- citizens (public)
- Other

15. Specify what are the negative influences of the policy implementation on the above indicated stakeholders *

16. In relation to this policy, do you identify other trends or initiatives that have impact on land use, but which are coming from the bottom (e.g., local groups, private actors) outside the authorities? *

17. Describe what are the effects of the policy implementation on land use / land cover changes. In other words, what underlying pathways of change are to be expected (e.g. in case of energy policy, an increase in biofuel production may result in land conversion to agriculture, or in a shift from food to energy crops). *

18. Any other comments?

19. Please enter your email address

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